

Women and Agency: A Study of Women's Reproductive Lives in Assam

Adishree Borgohain and Sarmistha Das

A woman's reproductive health is an important aspect of her overall physical and mental wellbeing and should be understood within the wider socio-economic, political and behavioral context of her life. The ability of women to make decisions and lifestyle choices in terms of her reproductive health will be discussed in this paper vis-à-vis her agency, i.e., autonomy over her own body and fertility. This notion of reproductive agency will be explored via the parameters of education, occupation and age of marriage to shed light on how non-biomedical factors have a crucial impact on reproductive health. The paper will to unpack the existing discourse of reproductive health in Guwahati city of Assam through in-depth qualitative interviews conducted by the authors with women of selected areas of the city. It will also critically examine the government intervention to improve the reproductive health status of the women in the city through its various policies, programmes and discuss whether and how it has impacted the women's reproductive health status.

Keywords: Reproductive health, contraceptive behavior, agency, education, Assam

Introduction

Women's reproductive health is an important aspect of her overall physical, mental and emotional well-being. It cannot be understood solely as a biological phenomenon—it is entwined with social, cultural, and political practices and with socially and culturally prescribed meanings and experiences (Braun et al., 2003; Ussher, 2006). The place of women in society, women's rights, and gender equality are central to the ability to exercise control over reproductive choices and lifestyles, including the ability to choose sexual partners, access to contraception and abortion, and the number of children born (Chrisler et al., 2020). Systemic and structural issues, such as access to quality health services (WHO, 2014), privacy and confidentiality, and representations of girls and women in the media, also influence reproductive health. Thus, reproductive health cannot be limited to biomedical factors only but needs to be understood within a wider array of socioeconomic, cultural, political, personal, and interpersonal factors, all having implication on one's reproductive health.

Adishree Borgohain is Assistant Professor at the Department of Sociology, Royal Global University, and Dr. Sarmistha Das is Assistant Professor at the Department of Sociology, Tezpur University, Assam, India. [Email: adishree.borgohain@yahoo.com]

The reproductive health of women is contingent upon various social determinants like educational levels, age of marriage, the autonomy the women enjoy in terms of their health decisions and mobility as well as the support they receive from their wider families. Wang and Pillai (2001); Wang (2004) have pioneered in their efforts to study the different socio- structural conditions conducive to women's reproductive health and highlighted a few crucial factors which condition reproductive health like education, modernisation and gender equality to understand the effect these have on the reproductive rights of women. Their analysis of gender equality sheds light on how gender relationships are embedded in social, economic and political institutions and are reinforced through everyday interactions. The extent of gender equality has a direct impact on the women's ability to determine the number and spacing of their children and sheds light on how it impacts 'agency' and self-determination of women. This notion of agency is crucial for women in terms of their health and well-being as it informs of their own ability to make decisions and choices with no restrictions from outside factors.

In this paper, the ability of women to make her own decisions in terms of her sexual and reproductive health has been analysed using the concept of 'agency' which is informed by Foucault's idiom of microphysics of power (Foucault, 1977) which is structured under Bandura's agentic perspective (Bandura, 2001; Paul et al, 2015). This theory of Foucault argues that power is strategic and tactical rather than acquired, preserved and possessed and the idiom is suitable when describing the power dynamics at the micro-level, which can refer to the community and family setting here (Paul et al 2017, 312). Agency can thus be understood as a form of power and a resource that is either shared between people- collective or is a capacity of the self- individual (Maxwell & Aggleton, 2010). Here, it needs to be kept in mind that applying strategies and tactics under the concept of agency is useful to disentangle women's capacity to make reproductive decisions and thereby understand what influences and choices are available to them within the wider community and how they navigate their choices in the wider community. Bandura's 'agentic perspective' has been adapted to fit the Indian context considering individual and collective agency (Omer-Salim, Suri, Dadhich, Faridi & Olsson, 2014). This is what this paper seeks to critically examine the concept of reproductive agency and how women exercise their agency in terms of their reproductive choices like contraception, spacing of children, abortion as well as family planning decisions within the family and wider community.

From Population Control to Reproductive Health

The rise of the second feminist movement in the 1960's brought issues like fertility, control over one's own body and accessibility of safe abortions and workplace safety into the spotlight. This marked the beginning of a heightened consciousness about women's rights and gender equality over all aspects of public and private life, including women's control over their own body and reproductive health. It eventually led to a shift in the focus of international population experts from population control to improving quality-of-life issues (Petchesky 1995; Gordon 1976; Ussher, et al, 2020; Ussher, 2023).

Women's health advocates began promoting a holistic approach to reproductive health, expanding the conversation beyond motherhood and childbearing. The emphasis

on a multi-sectoral model of reproductive health gained ground which would address the wider set of economic, social and familial circumstances which play a vital role in women's health seeking practices and culminated in the International Conference on Population and Development (ICPD), 1994 in Cairo (UN 1994). The ICPD introduced the concept of reproductive health on a global stage, shifting the focus from population and demographic policies to that of gender equality, women's empowerment and promotion of reproductive health. This conference was a watershed moment in bringing the limelight on reproductive health as it ushered forth a new orientation to the reproductive health agenda whereby the role of women was highlighted, not just as beneficiaries of services but as active agents of change.

In India, the legacy of sexual and reproductive health is heavily laced with the family planning programmes undertaken by the newly independent nation. The initial focus on demographic targets by the state led to the crisis of forced sterilisation during the Emergency period (1975-77) and caused a lot of havoc and distrust on the state's health orientation. As a result, the subsequent family planning programmes in the 1980's adopted a more 'voluntary' approach for acceptance of family planning goals among the people. India is also a signatory of the ICPD Agenda in the 90's which led a shift from the numerical, medical and method specific approach in the family planning programs to that of a gender sensitive, community based reproductive health approach whereby encouragement (as opposed to target-based goals and incentives) was given to keep family sizes small and the aim was to empower women to achieve their family planning goals (Rishyasinga, 2000; Ramasubban & Jejeebhoy, 2000). Despite the efforts made in policy reform, many experts argue that the state's reproductive health initiatives remain focused on short term indicators such as Maternal Mortality Rates (MMR), safe deliveries and pre-natal care. The broader questions on gender equality and women's rights and empowerment remain under-addressed, leaving gaps in addressing long-term issues like female literacy, good nutrition, financial autonomy as well as agency over one's body and life choices. These are critical components of women's reproductive health throughout their lifecycles, but they are often side-lined in the state's health policies.

In Assam as well, the MMR is a prominent indicator of the state's reproductive health in general and as per the Sample Registration System (SRS), Registrar-General of India (RGI-SRS), the state has recorded the second highest MMR amongst all other states at 167 deaths per lakh live births for the period 2022 (SRS 2019-21 report). The fifth round of the National Family Health Survey show that the performance indicators of maternal health in the state, such as receiving antenatal care (63%) is lower than the national average which is at 70% nation-wide (NFHS-5, 2019-2021). Additionally, even the percentage of women who are married before the legal age of marriage in Assam has increased from 30.8% (NFHS-4, 2015-16) to 31.8% reported in NFHS-5 while the national average declined from 26.8% (NFHS-4) to 23.3% during NFHS-5. All these factors highlight the poor reproductive health practices amongst some sections of the population which is contributing to a high maternal death rate in the state, especially in terms of home deliveries and early marriages of women.

The focus thus, remains on the immediate performance factors influencing the

MMR of the state to the sidelining of more long-term socio-cultural factors which have a crucial impact on women's reproductive health. This paper will try to address some of those gaps and also attempt to analyse the reproductive health status of the women in Guwahati by studying the factors of education, literacy and agency of the women in making life choices like marriage and child-spacing vis-à-vis the wider state policies and norms prevailing in the city. The study is a part of a doctoral research conducted during 2021-2023. In doing so, it hopes to understand how those factors have a long-term impact on the reproductive health of the women of the city throughout their life cycles.

Method

Study

Setting This paper draws upon data derived from doctoral research conducted in Guwahati, the largest city in Assam, situated in India's northeastern region. Guwahati is delineated into six health zones (Standard Reports, NHM, Assam, 2019), from which two were purposively selected for this investigation. The Sonapur Health Zone was chosen due to its unique status as Guwahati's sole district hospital with an adjacent Primary Health Centre (PHC) and a dedicated gynecology ward serving a significant semi-rural populace. The Dhirenpara Zone constituted the second selection, primarily due to its unique position as the city's sole sub-district hospital (First Referral Unit) which was fully and exclusively committed to maternal health services. The selection of Guwahati was predicated on its status as Assam's preeminent and most developed city, possessing optimal health infrastructure, comprehensive facilities, and qualified personnel for the effective management of reproductive health challenges. Furthermore, as the capital city of Assam, its diverse demographic composition is conducive for assessing reproductive health concerns across a spectrum of socio-cultural groups residing in the state.

Study Participants

The study's sample is constituted by married women between the ages of 15 and 49 years, encompassing both those who had given birth and expectant mothers. This specific age demographic was selected because it represents the conventionally recognized reproductive years for women. The inclusion of married women was justified by the prevailing social context in India, where reproductive health concerns, particularly regarding pregnancies and sexual activity, are predominantly acknowledged within the institution of marriage. The participants were drawn from three distinct socio-cultural linguistic groups: Assamese women, Bengali Muslim women, and the tribal women of Assam. The selection of women for the study was achieved through snowball sampling and direct assistance from local ASHA workers and medical doctors in the research localities. The primary interviewees comprised young mothers accessing reproductive healthcare services, such as maternity, parturition, antenatal, and postnatal care, at the Sonapur District Hospital or the Dhirenpara FRU. A strategic preference was given to mothers undergoing institutional delivery or receiving postnatal care. Furthermore, a series of follow-up interviews were implemented with

selected participants to expand upon themes inadequately addressed in the initial discussions and to validate qualitative data, thereby enhancing methodological reflexivity.

Data Collection

Data were collected through in-depth interviews, informal group discussions, and interviews with women and their accompanying individuals. Within the hospital settings, the researcher conducted interviews by completing a semi-structured interview schedule based on direct engagement with the participants. Subsequent follow-up interviews were facilitated either remotely via phone or through in-home visits to the women. These interviews were systematically conducted between March 2021 and September 2023. Insights into their reproductive health-seeking attitudes and behaviors were derived from their self-reported symptoms, manifestations of illness, and perceived ease of access to reproductive health services. Through this comprehensive data gathering, the study sought to elucidate women's conceptualizations of reproductive health challenges, their interpretations of sexuality, the influence of societal norms and prescriptions, and the overarching impact of both state policies and community structures on their daily exercise of reproductive agency.

Table 1: Total Respondents from both field sites

No of respondents	Sonapur District Hospital	Dhirenpara FRU
75 women	31	44

Table 2: Distribution of women across different categories

Ethnicity	No of respondents
Assamese	33
Bengali Muslim	26
Tribal	16
Total	75

Findings

This section examines the factors that shape the agency women exercise over their reproductive health. It is crucial to highlight that a woman's reproductive agency is strongly influenced by social determinants, including her level of education, age at marriage, and occupational status, which is often tied to her financial autonomy. The discussion focuses on how these key factors—specifically, a woman's age at marriage, her literacy level, and her employment status—affect her ability to make informed reproductive choices and decisions. By exploring these dimensions, we can better understand how social conditions empower or limit women's agency in their reproductive lives. It also offers an insight into the role of the state in providing reproductive health services and assess their shortcoming in improving the overall health status.

Marriage patterns

In India, early marriage continues to be the norm despite laws stipulating the legal age of marriage to be 18 years for females and 21 years for males. Early marriages usually result in compromised agency and autonomy for women. A study on the Indian multi-state shows that there has been a close association between early marriages of women and their reduced level of agency and autonomous decision making regarding their reproductive lives (Santhya, Rajob, Acharya, Jejeebhoy, Ram & Singh, 2010). Such early marriages indicate that sexual activity commences at an early age for many of the women. In India, the onset of sexual activity occurs largely within the context of marriages which is consistent with the strong emphasis placed on female 'purity' and chastity, sanctioned by family elders (Jejeebhoy 2000, 44).

In this study, 40.78% of the respondents were married below the legal age of eighteen years, between the ages of 14-17 years. Early marriages usually result in early pregnancies, compounded by low literacy levels and financial dependence. As a result, young women usually become prone to making reproductive decisions which are not always conducive for their health. For instance, when asked what the ideal age of marriage for girls was, one respondent called Premika (26 years old, Tribal woman) narrated that now that she is a mother herself, she would not consider marrying her daughter till at least 20 years of age or till she is old enough to take care of herself. She explained,

Our days were different, our parents did not pay attention to our education and married us off as soon as we started menstruating...that was the social custom of their times which all families followed. But now it is different for our children.

Premika herself studied till her 10th standard and was married off at 18 years of age and she depends on her husband who is a truck driver to fend for her needs as well as her two children, a 7-year daughter and a newborn son.

The social custom of marrying daughters after attaining puberty entailed that women in Assam were married off below the legal age which compromised on their education as well as deprived them of agency. Even though the incidence of dowry was lower in Assam in comparison to other states of the country, societal customs continue to reinforce women's lower social status and the expectation of motherhood.

The lack of family support can increase pressure on women in informal economies. For example, a 33-year-old Bengali Muslim widow, mother to two daughters, described her financial struggles. She works as a domestic helper and plans to marry off her eldest daughter at 16 years of age to alleviate her financial burden, allowing her to better care for her ailing mother. This case reflects how early marriage is often viewed as a financially practical solution for families facing economic hardships. In Assamese marriages, where the groom pays a bride-price, parents of girls often see marriage as a way to secure long-term financial stability.

Studies have shown that girls who marry in their adolescence tend to leave school midway and assume household chores after marriage while educated, working women favored to marry in their 20's. One 28 years old tribal pregnant woman called Tutu, who works in a clerical position in a government school explained,

I got married when I was 25 years old and have been working in a clerical position in a government school. I delayed my pregnancy because I wanted to be financially stable and physically ready to grow an infant.

Her story was in stark contrast to younger women who marry early and are less informed about methods to delay pregnancies. Research shows in India, the median age at marriage for women is 16 years and as many as 40 percent of all women aged 15-19 years are already married (IIPS, 1995). There is evidence that cohabitation also occurs early among rural and urban women, at around 15 years of age and on the whole, about half of all young women in India are thought to be sexually active by the time they are 18, and almost one in five by 15 years (Ramasubban and Jejeebhoy 2000, 44).

The latest round of National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5, 2019-21) shows a national decline in underage marriages, with 23.8% women marrying before attaining the legal age of 18 years as opposed to 26.8% reported in NFHS-4 (2015-16). However, in Assam, the percentage of underage marriages has increased from 30.8% reported in NFHS-4 (2015-16) to 31.8% reported in NFHS-5 (2019-21). This clearly indicates that early marriages are still highly prevalent in Assam as more and more women are getting married in their adolescent years, leading to a rise in teenage pregnancies and thereby exposing them to increased reproductive health risks.

Table 3: Age of marriage of women in both the field sites

Age	Sonapur	Dhirenpara	Total
Below 18 years	18	26	44 (58.66%)
Above 18 years	11	20	31 (41.73%)
Total	29	46	75

Table 4: Distribution of marriage age of women across different categories

Category of Women	Total No. of women in sample	Distribution of women who married above 18 years	Distribution of women who married below 18 years
Assamese women	33	17	16
Muslim (Bengali) women	26	3	23
Tribal women	16	11	5
Total	75	31	44

It can be inferred from Table 3 that 58.66% of women from the sample population have married below the legal age and Table 4 show that the highest proportion of underage marriages in this study has happened in the Muslim Bengali community, which is a minority group in Assam. It is worthwhile to note that out of the 26 women interviewed from this group, 23 (88.4%) of them were married below the legal age.

Additionally, out of the 33 Assamese women interviewed for this study, 48.4% of Assamese women were married below the legal age. It can also be inferred from Table 3 that there is a higher incidence of underage marriages in the Dhirenpara area, where

many migrants from nearby villages settle for better opportunities. These women often follow traditional practices, such as early marriage and childbirth and carework for the family. By contrast, the Sonapur area is a peri-urban space which is more rural and home to long-settled Assamese and tribal populations and has a lower rate of underage marriages. The residents in Sonapur, having become more accustomed to modern education, are less likely to consider late marriage unusual, unlike those in Dhirenpara, where migrant populations often adhere to older traditions.

Research indicates that in Assam, the reason for underage marriage is mostly cultural while the key role is poverty and a lack of education. Assam has a very unsustainable and precarious livelihood situation, majorly attributable to the local geography. It also hosts a large migrant population (Bengali Muslims) whereby inadequate access to education for children coupled with poverty makes them highly vulnerable to marrying off young girls who are often perceived as a burden.

Underage marriages exacerbate the problem of poverty and illiteracy among women and worsen the problems of maternal and child health outcomes. The problem of underage marriage is directly proportional to the maternal mortality rate of the state which is the highest in the country. In response to this ongoing issue, the current government implemented a strict ban on underage marriages starting in January 2023. This crackdown has resulted in numerous arrests of husbands and parents involved in such marriages where girls were wed before reaching the legal age of 18 (Goli & Singh, 2023). Unfortunately, these measures have also led to distressing consequences, including reports of deaths, reflecting the complexities and challenges of enforcing the new regulations.

Literacy and occupational backgrounds

A sound educational background is pertinent for the exposure of women to crucial information regarding good health seeking practices and choices in life. It increases their empowerment levels by widening their scope of becoming financially viable and also helps them in making educated, informed choices about many aspects of their lives like marriage, choice of partners, when to have children and how many, etc. In this study, 57.8% of the respondents have had a minimum of 10 years of schooling and the majority of the educated women who have studied till higher secondary have been seen to have later marriages (after 19 years of age) in comparison to their illiterate counterparts. For instance, a 25 years old Assamese respondent called Sumi who had just given birth to her first child narrated:

I got married immediately after completing my graduation and even though it was an arranged marriage, I was very careful to have a courtship for at least 4 months in advance before agreeing to get married to him. It was important for us to get along as I did not want a child for at least the first 3 years of marriage, wanting to focus on my education. And thankfully, I was able to plan out my first pregnancy how and when I wanted it, after completing my graduation in Assamese language.

Another participant called Marima (28 years old, pregnant Tribal woman) who was a practicing nurse, chose to quit her job when she became pregnant with her first child

at the age of 23. She waited for 4 years to plan her second pregnancy and explained that she was planning to rejoin services once her second child joined pre-school. She felt the need to complete her family size before rejoining her professional services. Her husband was a full-time taxi driver and required financial assistance to run the family of four. Marima's father was a vegetable vendor in the village but ensured that his daughter complete his higher secondary degree. She went on to pursue a nursing degree after she got married at 20 years as her in-laws were supportive and her husband was able to finance her education. Even though her husband earns enough now to sustain the family, she feels that once her children start going to school, the expense will rise, and she will have to pitch in her share to support the family.

These cases illustrate how the respondents who have access to education in their life can exercise agency in regards their reproductive health choices and lifestyle. Women with adequate literacy levels were able to plan their family with their husbands and make more informed decisions regarding their health, life and family. There is a negotiating ground between motherhood and education for most respondents who have studied till higher secondary levels as they become more informed about its importance. This negotiating ground reflects Bandura's agentic lens (2001) through which women enact their reproductive agency within the existing power structures of the family and the wider community. Overall, the literacy rates for women have improved at 72% (NFHS-5, 2021) at a national level while 41% of women had more than 10 years of schooling. The overall rate of literacy for women in Assam is 77.2% (NFHS-5) which is well above the national average which corroborates with our study whereby 57.8% of the respondents have had 10+ years of schooling.

In contrast, women with lower levels of education or no formal schooling faced greater reproductive health challenges. A 23-year-old Bengali Muslim woman named Sahina described how she was married at a young age and had no opportunity to attend school. As a single mother and widow, she worked in two households to support her children and elderly mother, relying on her labor rather than education to sustain her family. However, there are many women in the study who have very low levels of education and there are 9 respondents who have had no formal education throughout their lives (Fig 3.2). 89% of these women belong to the Bengali Muslim community of Assam. A respondent Hasina (Bengali Muslim, 23 years old, pregnant with third child) stated,

We are married off in our communities at young ages, as young as 13 years old sometimes, when we hit puberty... where is the time to go to school? I have worked at construction sites with my mother from a young age and have married a raj mistri only.

She described how all her sisters too never went to school and worked from young ages to help run the family and attaining education was a very distant dream for them. Hasina is a kaamwali residing in the Dhirenpara area of Guwahati who relies on her labor rather than education to sustain and support her family with her husband.

Another interviewee called Jaya who was a 27 years old Assamese housewife, pregnant with her second child, explained,

I attained menarche in my 7th standard and my mother stopped me from going to school

immediately. That was the end of my student life forever. The next year, I was married to a peon working in a government college and conceived almost within 2 months.

Education takes a backseat for women when their bodies undergo puberty as their social roles of dutiful wife and mother is prioritised by society over their education. When further probed, a 24 years old Tribal woman called Illu who was 7 months pregnant, explained:

My family was reluctant to send me to school after attaining puberty because the government schools we attend have students from diverse religious and ethnic backgrounds... there has been many instances where the girl runs away with a boy from different religious background and gets married... what can the parents do then? So, they take precaution beforehand and stop schooling for the girls at an early state only.

The social pressure experienced by the parents to get their daughters married within their own communities was important, least they face humiliation and ex-communication from their communities for unfavorable marriages between different religious and ethnic groups. "Honour" of a family usually depended on whether a daughter was able to fulfil her social role of a good wife and mother, within marriages which were approved by the general community to which she belonged to. The burden of care work was also usually entrusted to the women from a very young age as a part of their training to become a good wife and mother before they got married and education almost always took a backseat.

Table 5: Distribution of educational qualification among the women in both fieldsites

Educational Qualification	Sonapur	Dhirenpara	Total
No education	—	9	9 (12%)
Below Class 10	8	14	22 (29.4%)
HSLC	13	12	25 (33.4%)
HS	7	7	14 (18.6%)
Graduate	3	2	5 (6.6%)
Total	31	44	75

In this study, it has been observed that 29.4% (Table 5) of the women had education levels below matriculate level. This low literacy rate coupled with adolescent pregnancies expose the young girls to many reproductive health risks like still birth, infant and maternal deaths due to their low awareness and knowledge levels. From Table 5, it is evident that in the Sonapur area, all respondents had some level of schooling, while the highest proportion of completely illiterate respondents (those with no formal education) belonged to the Bengali Muslim community. A significant number of women had completed their education up to the High School Leaving Certificate (HSLC) level, but many dropped out after reaching menarche, as they began preparing for marriage. There is a clear connection between early marriage and low literacy levels, which has a cascading effect, leading to poor reproductive health

outcomes and higher rates of adolescent pregnancies.

Additionally, the data shows a strong correlation between the lack of schooling and child marriage rates across districts in Assam. It has been observed that in Assam the average years of schooling and education for men and women stand at 8 years against the expected 12 years. An alarming observation from the NFHS-5 data has been made that shows a decline in the proportion of females and males with more than 12 years of education in the State over the 3rd and 4th rounds (Table 6). This decline in average years of schooling can be inferred to lead to early marriage and further increase the incidence of teenage motherhood and also more number of children born. Teenage pregnancy is high among females who both had no schooling or less than five years of schooling (44 %) and tend to decrease with higher educational attainment. As seen from the various NFHS rounds child bearing is higher among women with low educational attainment (e.g. 22 percent among females with no schooling and only 4 percent among females with more than 12 years of schooling, NFHS-5). This suggests that underage marriage is directly linked to low educational attainment, highlighting the causal relationship between the two factors.

Table 6: Percentage of Women in Assam with more than 12 years of schooling

NHFS-5	NFHS-4	NFHS-3
11.5	15.0	10.2

Source: NFHS 3, 4 & 5

In terms of occupation, Assamese women in the study were primarily homemakers, relying on their families for financial support. Their husbands were typically employed in the informal sector, working as ambulance drivers, peons, small traders, or salesmen. Many of these women were engaged in domestic work and sometimes assisted their husbands in running small shops or participating in agricultural activities. Among the tribal women interviewed, 63% worked in the informal sector as vegetable vendors, agricultural laborers, or small shop owners, giving them more financial independence compared to the Assamese women. However, this did not necessarily translate to improved living conditions, as many tribal women only engaged in economic activities when their husbands had passed away or when household funds were insufficient.

For the Bengali Muslim women interviewed, most were either housewives with little mobility or agency, under strict family guardianship, or they worked as domestic helpers or daily wage laborers at construction sites to support their families. The stark income disparity between the indigenous women and the Bengali Muslim migrant women was notable, with the latter living in unsanitary conditions and relying heavily on physical labor to survive and sustain themselves and their families.

Age of first pregnancy

The timing of a woman's first pregnancy has significant implications for her health and well-being. In this study, it has been noted that 40% of the women interviewed have had their first pregnancy below the legal age of 18 years, with the highest proportion of underage pregnancies belonging to the Bengali Muslim women's category (Table 7).

Early pregnancies often occur due to societal pressure, early marriages, and lack of reproductive agency. These pregnancies carry higher risks of maternal and infant mortality, as well as long-term health complications for the mother.

Early marriage and childbirth are less prevalent among the tribal and Assamese respondents, but the Bengali Muslim women remain significant contributors to the reproductive health challenges faced in Assam. The survey results of NFHS-5 show that Muslim women are more likely to have 0.8 children more than Hindu women and this comparatively high teenage pregnancy and motherhood among Muslim females is one of the factors that have sustained comparatively higher fertility rate among the Muslim women in Assam. While the Total Fertility Rate of Muslim women has declined from 2.93 (NFHS-4) to 2.38 (NFHS-5), it is interesting to note that muslim women's TFR in Assam is still the highest amongst all religious groups (e.g., the TFR of Hindu women is 1.59 and Christian women is 1.47 in the NFHS-5 round).

Table 7: Distribution of Women who had their first pregnancy below 18 years

Category of Women	Total Women Interviewed	Distribution of Women who had first pregnancy below 18 years
Assamese women	33	9
Bengali Muslim women	26	19
Tribal women	16	2
Total	75	30

Negotiating Agency in Reproductive Health

Agency is a crucial asset for women to exert control over their own bodies and fertility, thereby making conscious decisions and choices which will impact their reproductive health status. Feminist anthropological and sociological understanding of agency are central to understanding women not just as passive products of structural and cultural factors, but active participants in practices and decisions that affect their lives (Bourdieu, 1977; Frank 2006; Ortner, 2001). This section will discuss how the women in the sample group use various tactics and strategies to enact some agency over their reproductive choices and decisions, pertaining to contraceptive behaviour, family size as well as abortions.

Reproductive decisions and women

Motherhood and pregnancy are not just personal experiences but also reflect societal expectations and pressures placed on women. Many respondents in the study viewed having children as both fulfilling their personal reproductive desires and upholding their social responsibilities. Childbearing was often seen as a way to improve their social status within the family and community. It also allowed women to embody the societal roles of “mother” and “wife,” reinforcing the cultural norms of what it means to be a “good” woman, while helping them achieve the traditional goals of marriage and starting a family.

A 28 years old Assamese woman called Hima, who was a mother of two, expressed her personal joy in fulfilling her reproductive dreams:

I always wanted a daughter after I got married. My firstborn was a son, so I knew I had to try again to fulfill my dream. Thankfully, I'm blessed with a daughter this time.

Another respondent called Juri who was a 25 year old Tribal woman, when asked if having children was essential after marriage, stated, "It is the natural course of marriage, to have children and grow your family. If you don't have a child, society will speak ill of you, call you barren, and look down upon you in social gatherings". For most women, motherhood was seen as a strategy to bolster their social status, both in their households and within society.

A 31 years old Assamese woman called Neha, who had one son, described the immense pressure to have children:

I had been trying for a child for almost seven years. After getting married, I delayed starting a family for two years, but my mother-in-law started pressuring me and my husband to have children. We started trying, but I had two miscarriages and one stillbirth. I was miserable and even stopped attending family gatherings. Now that I'm finally a mother, I feel a sense of relief" (Assamese, 31 years old, mother of a son).

For many Assamese and tribal women, social pressure to have children was a significant influence. Reproduction and motherhood were often seen as rites of passage that helped women enhance their social status. This pressure frequently overshadowed their personal desires, causing them to jeopardize their reproductive health to meet societal expectations. One respondent called Pratiksha shared how her relationship with her in-laws improved after having a child:

After I had my first baby, my in-laws were kinder, and it improved my relationship with them. They treat me with more love now and even help take care of my daughter" (Assamese, 24 years old, pregnant with her second child).

Although having one child often reduced the immediate pressure to have another, societal norms continued to dictate family size and spacing of children. Many women tactically delayed a second pregnancy, using factors such as finances and health to negotiate a few years of respite before their second pregnancy in order to 'complete their' family size. This reflects how young women's agency remains constrained by social structures, where family and societal pressures shape their reproductive decisions. Women's fertility and reproductive processes were often tightly controlled by their families, reinforcing patriarchal norms that curbed their agency from an early age.

Influence of Kin and Family

The family is a crucial juncture from where the body of a woman is exerted control upon to regulate her fertility and reproductive processes, reinforcing patriarchal norms and thereby, curbing her agency from a very early age. For example, Rizwana, a 17 year-old Bengali Muslim mother, share her experience of external control of her family on her reproductive choices:

I got married a year ago and almost conceived immediately. After giving birth to a son, I thought I'd wait five years before having another child, but my mother-in-law insists that I have a daughter within two years and then undergo sterilisation. I have no choice but to comply. She controls all the decisions and even takes me to the doctor. My husband doesn't have a say either.

Rizwana's story illustrates the lack of agency young women often experience, particularly those who are financially dependent on their in-laws. In her case, her mother-in-law monitored every aspect of her reproductive health, including interactions with ASHA workers. Rizwana was unsure whether she could make her own decisions about family planning, as she had never been encouraged to do so. While she felt that having two children in her family was necessary, she did not want to have her second child for another 5 years and she also did not want to undergo the hysterectomy, yet she was not sure whether she would be able to follow through with her own choices in opposition to her mother-in-law's. It can be inferred from her interview that she was not aware of having agency over her own body, pregnancy or childbirth, even for spacing her children. Agency here entails that the respondents are able to make decisions about their fertile body and the reproduction process, at every step, without any external monitoring, chaperoning or restriction at all. This lack of awareness and autonomy is common among younger, newly married women, who often defer to older family members for guidance and decisions related to reproduction (Madhavan et al., 2003).

Another respondent called Shefali, a 25 years old Muslim Bengali woman who was pregnant for a second time, echoed similar sentiments.

I am going through with this pregnancy only because my in-laws want it. I am not interested at all otherwise.

This respondent already had a seven-year-old daughter and felt that her family was complete, but her mother-in-law pressured her to have another child—preferably a son. This external influence on such personal reproductive decisions objectifies women, reducing their identities to that of wives and mothers, and diminishes their control over their own bodies. It decreases their agency over their own body and reproduction and thus poses a serious concern for maintaining good reproductive health. It can also be inferred that the birth of one child does reduce the pressure on women to delay their second pregnancy, but kin-interference and social expectations bound them to social norms and structures, thereby informing their reproductive decisions and influencing their reproductive health (Patel, 1999).

Some respondents were aware of the need for family planning and child-spacing for the health of both mother and child. However, these decisions were often driven by external factors such as finances, family expectations, and even state policies, rather than the women's personal reproductive goals. One 28 year old tribal woman called Debobala explained that she had to opt for an abortion after her first child because her son was only 15 months old and also because she couldn't afford to raise another child so soon. Most of the women described the "ideal family" as consisting of two children—one boy and one girl. As Sumaina stated:

After this pregnancy, I will get sterilized, regardless of the sex of the child. Two children are the norm—our parents had four or five, but now two is just the right size" (Assamese,

28 years old, mother of one, pregnant with her second).

The findings in this study clearly demonstrate the successful internalization of the government's past efforts in promoting the two child policy norms and spacing between children. There is widespread social acceptance in having two children in Assam with a healthy gap of 3-4 years between the children which coincides with women's personal reproductive agendas of delaying the second pregnancy by a few years and the financial capabilities of the household. Most women accepted the idea of having two children, spaced about 3-4 years apart, aligning with both their personal and financial circumstances. This widespread social acceptance of the two-child policy is evident across Assam, with the size of the family being more important than the sex of the children for most women interviewed. The recent NHFS-5 data also reflects this shift, showing an improvement in the sex ratio, with 1020 females for every 1000 males in 2021.

In terms of decisions about family planning and fertility, most Assamese and tribal women stated that their decision to carry their pregnancy full term was a joint spousal decision and had no external familial influence. While younger mothers tended to start families soon after marriage, older respondents, particularly those having their second child, reported that family planning was carefully considered after their first child, based on their economic situation. It is also important to note here that although the wishes and advise of in-laws was important for the mothers in terms of family planning and spacing of children, all the reproductive health decisions of the Assamese and tribal women were taken by the wife with her husband jointly.

Use of Contraceptives

Respondents used a variety of contraceptive methods to control reproduction, including oral contraceptives, injectable contraceptives like Antara injection, intrauterine devices (IUDs), and hysterectomies. Among the women interviewed, 68.32% reported using contraceptives, with oral contraceptives being the most popular choice (56.5% of respondents). Many women favored oral contraceptives because they perceived it as non-invasive, compared to copper-T or IUDs, which were associated with pain and heavy bleeding.

While they were open and responsive to discuss their personal choices and various methods that they used for family planning, they rarely had one effective strategy to control reproduction. Although most women were aware of the availability of the contraceptives and other methods of family planning a few rued about the lack of support mechanism and guidance in family planning. In such cases the institutional spaces like hospitals, foot soldiers of the State like the ASHAs, ANMs and the informal group of friends help in generation and spread of information on the usage of contraception and its implication in family planning. Among the respondents 68.32 % of women used contraceptives and the oral contraceptives like Mala D and Overall L were the most popular products used by 56.5 % of the respondents from the field. The oral contraceptives were considered as the most favorable since they were noninvasive as the copper-T or hysterectomy. The fear of surgical insertion and associated health anomalies like pain and excessive bleeding have pushed most respondents to opt for

oral contraceptives.

A 22-year-old Assamese woman called Binapani stated: “Copper-T is painful and leads to bleeding, it is not safe” when probed, another respondent added “it is unnecessary because, it is very painful and there is heavy bleeding for days. I had it inserted after my first pregnancy, but it caused so much pain and bleeding that I decided to have it removed after 6 months. I now use pills instead”.

Hysterectomy emerged as another popular method of controlling reproduction, especially among women who had reached their ideal family size of two children. However, it was often the doctors or family members who encouraged women to undergo the procedure, indicating that the decision was not always the woman’s own. In these cases, the state’s family planning goals appeared to influence personal reproductive decisions, further limiting women’s agency.

The other forms of contraception mentioned by the respondents were abstinence and the Antara Injection. Few experienced mothers who were not inclined to medical methods of regulating their fertility mentioned about ‘abstinence’. Runmi, a 28 years old Assamese woman who was pregnant for the second time, said:

I sleep on the floor, separately from my husband on certain days of my cycle... usually for about a week after my menstruation is over. I learnt this technique from my friends. It worked for me as I wanted to wait for at least 5 years after my first child was born.

Another respondent called Morjima stated:

I tried the medicines, and my body did not feel well. I felt sick for months till I finally discontinued the pill. I and my husband practice periodic abstinence to manage unwanted pregnancies” (Bengali Muslim woman, 29, mother of three children).

In cases of unwanted pregnancies women took control of their bodies by orally taking pills and aborting the fetus, while others relied on surgical abortions. Early pregnancies, lack of gap between the children, financial insecurities were some of the common grounds for abortions. The most cited reasons for abortions among the respondents were inadequate income (46.9%), spacing of children (32.6%) and family size complete (16.3%) while a few respondents cited contraceptive failure (4.9%).

There are also cases in which the women were often caught unaware with bodily infringements. A 27 year old tribal woman called Riju narrated how she had extreme pain and bleeding after her delivery. When she approached a private clinic, she was told that she had an IUD inserted in her uterus. While she remembers talking about family planning, but she was not informed of the insertion of IUD into her body at the government hospital. Scholars like Zola, 1972; Pahor, 1999; Brubaker & Dillaway, 2009; Foucault, 1963 call this infringement of the women’s body through excessive medicalization of the female body. The need to control a women’s body through medical devices robs her of the agency over her own body and its functions and this had been a focal point of debate in many feminist discourses and exhibits how the core issue of women’s reproduction and population control is still implicitly prevalent in the state’s policy outcomes. It has been noted that most of the women who have had two children are informed by the doctors in both the hospitals to either go for a hysterectomy or opt for an IUD device. This showcases how agency over one’s reproductive body in terms

of future planning is again reduced. Such instances are often privy to the 86% of the respondents who have had negative feedback on the IUD and 19.56% had never heard of the same.

The current contraceptive use rate in India has increased from 54% (NFHS-4) to 67% (NFHS-5) which corroborates with our study whereby most of the respondents showed no hesitancy in discussing their personal reproductive health choices. But it was not the case for all as there were still a small proportion (28%) of respondents from the study who claimed to have never used contraception before or dismissed the topic shyly and 9.33% of the respondents have claimed to have never heard of what contraception or family planning is. It was interesting to note from the field that most women correlates the use of condoms with their husband's sexual loyalties. They shielded their husbands by reiterating that they were not unfaithful and hence did not need any condoms to protect themselves against sexual diseases.

The study indicates that the burden of family planning and fertility regulation still falls largely on a women's shoulders. The rationale behind usage of condoms is not grasped well by the respondents and raises concern about the need to dissipate more awareness on the matter. For traditional methods like abstinence, women need to be educated on the correct ovulation cycle for better regulation of their fertility and for modern methods, more discussion and counselling needs to prevail to understand which method would best suit a couple. This shows that there is still the need for creating more awareness. The state needs to scale up its efforts in providing safe, acceptable and non-discriminatory services to all women to ensure good reproductive health for women, even the adolescent and unmarried ones.

Role of State

The state plays a crucial role in promoting and improving women's reproductive health in terms of policy implementation, generating awareness and health care service delivery. Government programs such as the Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) and Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakaram (JSSK) provide free medicines and supplements, diagnostic services, and institutional deliveries, aiming to reduce maternal mortality and improve reproductive health outcomes. Asha workers serve as key intermediaries between the state and the women, encouraging institutional deliveries and promoting reproductive health awareness through community outreach. The women in the study were encouraged to opt for institutional deliveries from a very early stage through the services provided by the state and regularly reminded by the Asha workers through home-visits and monthly health camps. The Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) similarly provides cash incentives to all women who opt for institutional deliveries at the time of getting discharged from the hospital.

On paper, the state is invested in improving the maternal mortality status of the women and addresses it through many policy incentives and interventions. However, the state's implicit focus on population control and achieving numerical targets, such as the two-child policy, often influences women's reproductive decisions in subtle ways. Doctors and health workers frequently advise women to undergo sterilization after their second child, reinforcing the notion of an "ideal family size" of two children. While the state does not prompt any legal sanctions for families which have more

than two children, it takes indirect punitive measures to address the issue. For instance, Assam Government has recently amended the Assam Civil Services Act 1965 to pass a legislation whereby a family having more than two children after January 2021 is not eligible for government jobs or to contest panchayat elections.

Similarly, it has been noted in the field how early marriages increase the likelihood of maternal deaths and ill-health due to underage mothers begetting children at a very early age. The state's efforts to ban underage marriages have also created a complex dynamic. As Assam has the second highest MMR in the country (RGI SRS, 2019-21), the state government has undertaken a drive on December 2022 to completely ban underage marriages and book the relatives and husbands under the Prohibition of Child Marriage Act of 2006 with a minimum sentence period of two years for marrying girls between the age of 14-18 years. There has been a mass string of arrests with much public outcry when the husbands and fathers of these underage girls were arrested, amounting to approximately 4000 arrests between 2022-23 in two major crackdowns against child marriage. These measures caused much emotional and physical distress to the underage women who were pregnant at that time, and many had committed suicide out of fear of the state's actions (Borauh & Meharban, 2023). As such, the current regime has taken the decision to ban underage marriages under the Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, 2012 (POSCO Act) completely since February 2022 and has led to many arrests and deaths of husbands and parents of such underage girls who had married before the legitimate age of 18 years. Thus, it is crucial to recognise the draconian measures adopted by the state to ensure its agendas being adopted widely by the general populace.

It is pertinent to recognise how the state works insidiously to exert soft coercion on a woman's body and reproductive health to implement their own targets and policy agendas to improve demographic figures at a surface level. While the state has put in many efforts to improve the reproductive health of the women through legal means as well as awareness programs, the benefits of its policies pose a shadowy ground for the women who are distrustful, especially after the recent crackdowns led by the government. The positive steps taken by the state become lost in the heavy-handed tactics they adopt to promote their reproductive health agendas.

Conclusion

The study sheds light on the reproductive health status of women in Guwahati, emphasizing the interplay between education, agency, and social norms in shaping women's reproductive choices. Women with higher levels of education were more likely to delay marriage and pregnancies, make informed health decisions, and exert greater agency over their reproductive lives. In contrast, those with lower education levels and financial dependence were more vulnerable to early marriages, early pregnancies, and limited agency in family planning. As seen from the various NFHS rounds, child bearing is higher among women with low educational attainment (e.g. 22 % among females with no schooling and only 4 % among females with more than 12 years of schooling, NFHS-5) and therefore disparities in educational attainment levels compound the impact of economic inequality on child bearing and population growth.

It must be noted that for the women of a third world country like India, the agenda

of reproductive health was absent in the narratives of the Indian feminist struggles which focused on “women’s overall health” unlike the western counterparts who focused on attaining reproductive rights and body agency via the feminist struggles. In India, the focus was on improving women’s economic role, land rights and greater share in education as a tool to improve the overall health of women (Qadeer, 1998). As such, reproductive health is viewed within the narrow confines of mother and child health which gets reflected via-a-vis the health initiatives. While the state’s reproductive health programs have improved access to services, the implicit focus on population control and the two-child policy continues to restrict women’s autonomy over their bodies. The state must adopt a more holistic approach that emphasizes women’s rights, education, and long-term health outcomes rather than merely focusing on short-term goals like reducing maternal mortality.

Additionally, the dismal MMR of Assam (highest in the country) is a crude indicator of the bleak reproductive health status of the state and points to the fact that there remains much to be done. There is a gap in provision of reproductive health services and its effective utilisation and signifies the need for generating more awareness for preventive care at the individual level which is a crucial task that the state is lagging behind. The state must adopt a more holistic approach that emphasizes women’s rights, education, and long-term health outcomes rather than merely focusing on short-term goals like reducing maternal mortality. There is a pressing need to increase awareness and education about reproductive health, particularly in marginalized communities. Programs must go beyond promoting contraceptive use to address the socio-cultural and economic factors that limit women’s reproductive agency. Only by empowering women through education and support can meaningful improvements in reproductive health be achieved.

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